

21 January 2025

Unboxing AI-native networks: Pairing XAI Methods to Data Types for Edge-Cloud Orchestration

Lazaros Liatsas¹, Godfrey M Kibalya¹, Angelos Antonopoulos¹

1. Nearby Computing S.L

Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in next generation cloud-native mobile networks has transformed network and service orchestration, driving the evolution towards fully automated zero-touch operations. As the AI in telecommunications market rapidly expands, the demand for transparency in AI decision-making, known as eXplainable AI (XAI), becomes of paramount importance. XAI mitigates the "black box" nature of AI models, ensuring transparency, crucial for regulatory compliance, user acceptance and system improvement. In this article, motivated by the diversity of data types in cloudnative orchestration scenarios (i.e., tabular, time-series and raw text), we explore the impact that the different data types may have on the selection of the appropriate XAI technique. In addition, we classify and discuss XAI techniques suitable for each data type, outlining a series of use cases in edge/cloud orchestration. Finally, we present two real-world proof-of-concept use cases, demonstrating the benefits that XAI can bring to cloudnative networks. Our contributions aim to facilitate the effective integration of AI in dynamic environments, bridging the gap between AI model interpretability and practical deployment in next generation cloud-native networks.

Keywords

5g, 6g, cloud-native, communication, networking and broadcast technologies, computing and processing, edge computing, explainable ai, mec, network automation, zero-touch, zsm

Unboxing AI-native networks: Pairing XAI Methods to Data Types for Edge-Cloud Orchestration

Lazaros Liatsas*, Godfrey M. Kibalya*, Angelos Antonopoulos*

*Nearby Computing S.L.

Barcelona, Spain

Email: {lazaros.liatsas, godfrey.kibalya, angelos.antonopoulos}@nearbycomputing.com

Abstract—The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in next generation cloud-native mobile networks has transformed network and service orchestration, driving the evolution towards fully automated zero-touch operations. As the AI in telecommunications market rapidly expands, the demand for transparency in AI decision-making, known as eXplainable AI (XAI), becomes of paramount importance. XAI mitigates the “black box” nature of AI models, ensuring transparency, crucial for regulatory compliance, user acceptance and system improvement. In this article, motivated by the diversity of data types in cloud-native orchestration scenarios (i.e., tabular, time-series and raw text), we explore the impact that the different data types may have on the selection of the appropriate XAI technique. In addition, we classify and discuss XAI techniques suitable for each data type, outlining a series of use cases in edge/cloud orchestration. Finally, we present two real-world proof-of-concept use cases, demonstrating the benefits that XAI can bring to cloud-native networks. Our contributions aim to facilitate the effective integration of AI in dynamic environments, bridging the gap between AI model interpretability and practical deployment in next generation cloud-native networks.

Index Terms—5G, 6G, ZSM, explainable AI, cloud-native, MEC, edge computing, zero-touch, network automation

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the 5G service-based architecture has paved the way for cloud-native mobile networks, driving the integration of cloud and edge computing into a unified telco-compute continuum. Moving towards next generation networks, 6G introduces advanced inherent network intelligence, significantly enhancing the role of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) in managing the complex ecosystem of cloud-native applications and network services [1]. Recent forecasts predict that the AI market in telecommunications will reach \$13.5 billion by 2028, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 40.4% during the forecast period [2]. This anticipated growth highlights the pivotal role of AI in unlocking the full potential of 6G networks and edge/cloud computing environments, enabling optimized performance, scalability, and resource orchestration.

The widespread adoption of AI, along with the “black-box” nature of many AI models, have stressed the need for transparent and interpretable decision-making. Explainable AI (XAI) has emerged as a critical tool to address these challenges by enabling human users to understand, trust, and validate AI outputs [3]. This transparency is essential for building user confidence, ensuring regulatory compliance, as well as

facilitating the debugging and improvement of AI models. Hence, as AI becomes more integrated in 6G networks and edge/cloud environments, the demand for XAI solutions grows proportionally.

A wide range of XAI techniques exists, each tailored to clarify the decision-making processes of complex AI models. However, the choice of a particular XAI technique highly depends on the underlying *data type*. In the context of zero-touch network and service orchestration in edge/cloud environments, a diverse range of data types is usually considered, classified into three main categories: i) *tabular* data, characterized by their structured format with rows and columns, are prevalent in applications such as resource utilization logs, service performance metrics and customer usage records; ii) *time-series* data, which consist of sequential data points indexed by time, are crucial for monitoring temporal patterns in network traffic, sensor readings and system performance metrics; and iii) *raw text* data, which are usually generated by textual logs and system status updates, provide information in a human-friendly manner. To that end, the selection of the appropriate XAI technique (according to the data type) ensures accurate, meaningful explanations that enhance transparency and trust in AI-driven cloud-native orchestration. Understanding the interplay between data types and XAI techniques is critical to optimize the deployment and management of AI systems in these complex and dynamic environments. The surge in XAI has recently motivated some research works that provide overviews of XAI techniques in the field of 6G [3], [4], [5]. However, despite their novel insights on XAI taxonomies and on theoretical frameworks for the application of XAI in cloud-native networks, these studies neglect the interplay between the data type and the XAI methods.

Our contribution in this article is threefold: First, we provide a comprehensive classification of XAI techniques based on their suitability for different data types, i.e., tabular, time-series and raw text data. Second, we identify potential applications of these XAI techniques in edge/cloud scenarios, highlighting how specific techniques can enhance the interpretability of AI models in various contexts. Third, we present two real-world proof-of-concept use cases, demonstrating the benefits that XAI can bring in cloud-native networks. These contributions aim to bridge the gap between AI model interpretability and practical deployment in next generation cloud-native networks, ensuring that AI-driven innovations are both effective and trustworthy.

II. XAI BACKGROUND

The categorization of XAI techniques, illustrated in Fig. 1, is usually based on a variety of criteria that include: i) explanation scope (global vs. local), ii) model applicability (model-agnostic vs. model-specific) and iii) stage of model development (post-hoc vs. ante-hoc). In this section, we briefly discuss these different categories, providing a general background on XAI.

A. Explanation scope

Global and local techniques serve distinct purposes in interpreting ML models, based on their awareness scope.

Global techniques provide an overarching view of how the entire model behaves across the dataset. They aim to explain the general patterns and feature importance across all predictions made by the model. Global techniques are useful for understanding the overall decision-making process of the model, identifying which features are generally most influential, and gaining insights into model biases and tendencies.

Local techniques, on the other hand, focus on explaining individual predictions, aiming to understand why a particular instance was predicted in a specific way. Local techniques provide insights into the specific factors that influenced a prediction, highlighting the most relevant features for that instance. They are valuable for verifying the model's decisions on critical or sensitive cases, identifying instances where the model may have made errors, and improving trust and transparency in AI systems by offering intuitive explanations tailored to specific predictions.

B. Model applicability

The distinction between model-agnostic and model-specific techniques lies in their applicability and scope of interpretation.

Model-agnostic techniques are versatile and can be applied to any ML model, regardless of its type or complexity. These techniques focus on understanding the overall behavior of the model, such as feature importance or contribution to predictions, without relying on the specific internal workings of the model. Model-agnostic techniques are beneficial when working with a variety of models or when the internal architecture of the model is complex and not easily interpretable.

Model-specific techniques, on the other hand, are tailored to interpret specific types of models or families of models. These techniques often leverage the internal structure and operations of the model to provide detailed insights into its decision-making process. Model-specific techniques are advantageous for gaining deep insights into how a particular model classifies or predicts data, offering detailed explanations that align closely with the model's internal mechanisms.

C. Explanation timing

The distinction between post-hoc and ante-hoc techniques relates to when explanations are generated in relation to the model development process.

Post-hoc techniques are applied after the model has been trained and are independent of the model's training process. These techniques focus on interpreting the predictions of the model without altering its internal workings. Post-hoc techniques are versatile and can be applied to any trained model, making them suitable for interpreting complex models like deep neural networks where understanding internal mechanisms might be challenging.

Ante-hoc techniques, on the other hand, integrate interpretability into the model development process itself. These techniques aim to design and train models that are inherently interpretable or have built-in explanations. Methods like decision trees, rule-based models, and certain types of explainable neural networks fall into this category. Ante-hoc techniques prioritize transparency from the outset, making it easier to understand how the model makes decisions without requiring additional post-training interpretation. These techniques are particularly beneficial in applications where transparency and interpretability are critical requirements from the beginning, such as in healthcare or finance.

Fig. 1: XAI taxonomy

III. DATA TYPES AND XAI TECHNIQUES

In edge/cloud orchestration scenarios, *tabular data*, *time-series data* and *raw text data* constitute the three prominent data types. Each data type requires specific AI models for optimal handling and analysis. This section offers a comprehensive analysis of i) the structural characteristics of these diverse data types, and ii) how these types can be associated to specific AI models and, consequently, XAI techniques. Fig. 2 illustrates a visual colored-mapped association of the entire process.

A. Tabular data

Tabular data refer to data structured in a table format, consisting of rows and columns, where each row represents a unique record and each column represents a specific feature or attribute of the data. For analyzing and modeling tabular data, several AI models have proven to be particularly effective. **Gradient Boosting Machines (GBMs)** and **Random Forests** are popular thanks to their ability to handle high-dimensional data and capture complex interactions between features. These

Fig. 2: Selection of XAI technique based on the underlying data, their type and AI models

methods combine the predictions of multiple decision trees to improve accuracy and robustness. Additionally, **vanilla Neural Networks**, which are basic feedforward neural networks, are also suitable for tabular data. They can model non-linear relationships and learn complex patterns through multiple layers of interconnected neurons. These models are widely adopted for their effectiveness in making accurate predictions and their ability to generalize well across different types of tabular datasets. Hence, the following model-agnostic, post-hoc XAI techniques can be considered as more suitable for application in scenarios where tabular data are involved, taking into account the varying nature of the state-of-the-art AI models.

- 1) **SHAP** (SHapley Additive exPlanations) [6] is a powerful technique that interprets complex ML models. Based on Shapley values from game theory, SHAP attributes the prediction of an instance to its features in a fair and consistent manner by considering all possible combinations of features and their level of contribution to the prediction. SHAP values indicate the contribution of each feature, offering both local explanations (for individual predictions) and global explanations (for overall model behavior). This technique is model-agnostic and can be applied to a wide range of ML models, providing intuitive and actionable insights into how features influence predictions, thereby enhancing transparency and trust in the model.
- 2) **LIME** (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) [7] works by generating locally interpretable models around individual predictions. LIME slightly modifies the input data and observes the changes in predictions, using these modified samples to train a simple, interpretable model (e.g., a linear regression or a decision tree). This local surrogate model approximates the behavior of the complex model in the vicinity of the specific instance, providing insights into which features contribute most to the prediction. LIME is model-agnostic, i.e., it can be used with any ML model, making it a versatile tool for understanding and explaining individual predictions.

- 3) **Counterfactual explanations** [8] provide insights by identifying minimal changes to an input that would alter the model's prediction. Essentially, they answer "what-if" questions by showing how modifying specific features can lead to different outcomes. For instance, in a loan approval model, a counterfactual explanation might reveal that slightly increasing an applicant's income would change the decision from rejection to approval. This technique helps users understand the decision boundaries of the model and the critical factors that affect the predictions. Counterfactual explanations are intuitive and actionable, enabling users to grasp the conditions under which different results occur, thus enhancing the transparency and interpretability of complex ML models.

B. Time-series data

Time-series data consist of sequences of data points indexed in time order, capturing the temporal dynamics and patterns inherent in the data. For analyzing time-series data, **Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)** and **Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs)** are particularly effective. RNNs, including their variants, like **Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)** networks and **Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs)**, are designed to handle sequential data by maintaining a hidden state that captures information from previous time steps, enabling them to learn temporal dependencies. TCNs, on the other hand, utilize convolutional layers with dilated convolutions to capture long-range temporal patterns, while maintaining computational efficiency and stability during training. All these techniques fall under the umbrella of deep learning and, thanks to their recurrent or temporal nature, they can model the sequential nature of time-series data, enabling accurate forecasting, anomaly detection, and pattern recognition. Therefore, the following model-specific XAI techniques tailored for convolutional networks, are considered state-of-the-art solutions for providing explanations of such models.

- 1) **Integrated Gradients** [9] is a technique used to interpret deep learning models, particularly neural networks. It aims to attribute the prediction of a model to its input

features by integrating gradients along the path from a baseline input (such as a zero or average value) to the actual input. By computing the cumulative gradient, it quantifies the contribution of each feature to the prediction. This method ensures that the attributions are sensitive to feature importance and satisfy desirable properties like sensitivity and implementation invariance. Integrated Gradients are particularly useful for models with non-linear behavior, providing clear and precise explanations that help users understand how specific input features influence the model’s decisions.

- 2) **Grad-CAM** (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping) [10] is designed to interpret deep learning models, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Although Grad-CAM is mainly used in computer vision tasks (because of the widespread adoption of CNNs for such applications), it can also be applied to any model that incorporates convolutional layers, e.g., TCNs. Grad-CAM works by computing the gradients of the target class score concerning the feature maps of a convolutional layer. These gradients are then used to produce a feature map that indicates the importance of different regions in the input. In time series, “feature maps” might represent temporal filters that focus on specific patterns or time intervals. Hence, instead of spatial regions, Grad-CAM would highlight time segments.
- 3) **DeepLIFT** (Deep Learning Important Features) [11] attributes a model’s output to its input features by comparing the activation of each neuron to a reference activation. DeepLIFT assigns contribution scores to each input feature, indicating their impact on the prediction. Unlike gradient-based methods, which can suffer from issues like vanishing gradients, DeepLIFT provides stable and consistent attributions by considering the difference in activation from a reference point. This technique provides insights on how each feature affects the model’s decisions, rendering it particularly useful for complex models with non-linear behavior, thus enhancing the interpretability and transparency of deep learning models.

C. Raw text data

Transformers and Large Language Models (LLMs) [12] have emerged as powerful AI models for handling and manipulating raw text data. Their architecture, especially the self-attention mechanism, enables them to capture long-range dependencies and contextual relationships within the text, which are essential for understanding and generating human language. Unlike traditional models that rely on sequential data processing, transformers can process entire sequences of text simultaneously, allowing for more efficient and comprehensive analysis. This makes them particularly well-suited for a range of natural language processing tasks, including translation, summarization, and sentiment analysis. The ability of transformers to handle vast amounts of text data and extract meaningful patterns has revolutionized the field, setting a new standard for AI applications involving textual data.

Given that the **attention mechanism** is a core component of transformers and LLMs, it naturally lends itself to XAI as a

global, ante-hoc technique thanks to its inherent interpretability. The attention mechanism provides a transparent way to understand how these models make decisions by highlighting which parts of the input text the model focuses on when producing an output. By visualizing attention weights, the most influential words or phrases that the model considers can be identified, thereby enhancing interpretability. This makes the attention mechanism an effective XAI technique, native to transformers and LLMs, as it directly aligns with their operational principles and provides a clear, intuitive understanding of their inner workings.

Recent advancements in literature have explored the application of transformers in time-series data beyond textual information [13]. The results have been very promising, hence enabling the adoption of the inherently interpretable attention mechanism in time-series data.

IV. XAI APPLICATIONS IN EDGE/CLOUD SCENARIOS

This section presents a series of use cases that illustrate how XAI techniques can be integrated into cloud-native networks and, particularly, in edge/cloud orchestration and lifecycle management processes to optimize resource utilization, improve energy efficiency, and enhance decision-making in dynamic computing environments. A summary of these use cases is also provided in Table I.

A. Network security and anomaly detection

Anomalies in the state of modern networks can either be caused from system malfunctions or due to third-party intrusions, hence the ability to detect such anomalies, or even predict them, is vital for system reliability and security. AI has been proven a useful tool for the task of anomaly detection, where given a system’s current state, failure or security breaches are automatically detected. However, with the huge number of system variables, these AI models fail to pinpoint the location or the root-cause of the anomaly. XAI techniques attributing feature importance scores can be utilized for this purpose. Considering the system variables comprising the current system state (e.g., infrastructure configurations, network topology, traffic information, user statistics, etc.) and their tabular format, the **SHAP** technique would be an appropriate solution.

B. Dynamic resource allocation

Dynamic resource allocation is critical for optimizing the performance and efficiency of networks, particularly in cloud-native environments. By ensuring that each service is always provisioned with the necessary resources, dynamic allocation prevents violations of Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, thereby maintaining service reliability and user satisfaction. Such QoS violations can be predicted through AI models, either through classifying a current snapshot of the underlying system, or predicting a performance indicator, such as end-to-end latency. These snapshots may include the current resource utilization per service/node, workload statistics and various system configurations. In such scenarios, it would be

TABLE I: XAI Applications in Cloud-native Use Cases

Use Case	Actions	Data	Type	Suggested Technique
Network security and anomaly detection	Identify and locate the root-cause behind system failures and/or security breaches.	Infrastructure configurations, network topology, traffic information and user statistics	Tabular	SHAP
Dynamic resource allocation	Provide actionable explanations on AI predictions of QoS violations and performance degradation.	Current resource utilization per node/service, workload statistics and various system configurations	Tabular	Counterfactual Explanations
Efficient workload forecasting	Fine-tune forecasting models, tailored to the underlying infrastructure and applications towards speed and cost efficiency.	Historical data of resource utilization and workload related metrics such as call rate and user traffic	Time-series	Integrated Gradients
Enriched and user-friendly logging	Enrich raw logs with user-friendly explanations as well as suggested actions.	Pre-processed logs from various sources across the network infrastructure	Raw text	Attention Mechanism

of great value to accompany the violation predictions with specific explanations that identify the cause. Furthermore, by utilizing **counterfactual explanations**, the system can receive actionable feedback on which services are in need of resource allocation and can even quantify the exact amount.

C. Efficient workload forecasting

The ability to forecast workload is critical in current network and cloud environments, enabling proactive resource management and ensuring optimal performance. By accurately predicting future workloads, organizations can dynamically adjust resource allocations to meet demand without over-committing resources. This approach not only enhances the responsiveness and reliability of services, but also minimizes waste of resources, leading to significant cost savings and reduced energy consumption. Advanced AI/ML models for forecasting allow for more precise predictions by analyzing historical data and identifying patterns in time-series of system metrics. However, it is not always clear which system metrics are correlated with the forecasting target (e.g., CPU utilization, call rate) and these correlations can vary between different applications and infrastructure. By applying time-series tailored techniques such as **Integrated Gradients** on a general forecasting model, we can extract valuable information on feature importance, as well as temporal insights. Such insights can then lead to the design of fine-tuned models that are faster, less complex and therefore more cost-efficient.

D. Enriched and user-friendly logging

The advent of LLMs and the attention mechanism has the potential to revolutionize the generation of enriched, user-friendly logs in next generation networks. By leveraging the ability of LLMs to process and analyze vast amounts of network data, combined with the **attention mechanism**'s capacity to focus on critical features, these models can automatically generate detailed, context-aware logs that enhance network visibility and troubleshooting efficiency. This approach facilitates real-time identification of anomalies, dynamic adaptation to network conditions, and the creation of intuitive, human-readable logs that improve the decision-making process for network operators. Furthermore, the integration of LLMs into

6G networks can support the automation of log interpretation, reducing operational complexity and enabling more proactive network management strategies.

V. PROOF-OF-CONCEPT: TWO USE CASE EXAMPLES

To further highlight and quantify the potential of XAI in cloud-edge orchestration scenarios, we have focused on two of the aforementioned use cases, i.e., i) *efficient workload forecasting*, and ii) *dynamic resource allocation*. In this section, we provide the details and the experimental results that showcase the practical gains that XAI can bring in cloud-native scenarios.

A. Reduction of workload forecasting models through Integrated Gradients

Workload forecasting can be defined as the task of predicting the workload of an application or system node at a future timestep (or multiple timesteps) by exploiting available historical data and patterns. This can be either tackled by univariate auto-regressive time-series forecasting, or by considering a multivariate time-series problem, where more than one metric is taken into consideration for predicting the target workload metric. In our experiment, we investigate the multivariate case as our target is to exploit XAI for the identification of the correlated metrics that can improve the forecasting accuracy. As target workload metric, we have selected the CPU utilization (which is a common target metric in cloud-native scenarios), while our goal is to select a subset of the initial feature set and a smaller lookback window size for the forecaster, so as to achieve a much faster, reduced forecasting model by exploiting insights provided by the Integrated Gradients technique.

We have considered the BitBrains dataset [14], as it contains trace data from multiple Virtual Machines (VMs) and, apart from the CPU utilization, memory utilization and network received/transmitted throughput have been also chosen as feature metrics for the forecaster. LSTM, one of the most popular RNN architectures, is selected as our forecasting AI model. A standard training procedure is followed for the LSTM model, dividing the BitBrains data for a single VM into a train and test set, while utilizing the Huber loss function and the Adam optimizer. We keep all hyperparameters constant

Fig. 3: Integrated Gradients attributions scores

between the initial and reduced model training, as our main goal is to observe the effects of the model reduction in the number of features and the time-window size.

Following the training of the LSTM model, we apply the Integrated Gradients to generate feature and timestep attributions for each sample in the test set. Integrated Gradients work by integrating the gradients of the model’s output with respect to its inputs along a path from a baseline (usually a zero or neutral input) to the actual input. This path-based integration captures the model’s sensitivity to changes in input values, producing feature attributions that indicate the amount each input feature contributes to the prediction. The result is a set of values that indicate which parts of the input have the highest impact to the model’s decision. In order to retrieve global insights on the model’s decision-making, the local explanations are averaged through the whole test set.

Fig. 3 illustrates the final output of the Integrated Gradients visualized as a color-map to distinguish and make visible the importance of both features and timesteps. Analyzing Fig. 3, we may conclude that the reduced model can be designed by considering only the two most important features (i.e., CPU and network transmitted throughput), while the time-window size can be reduced from 36 to the 12 latest timesteps. Replicating the exact same training procedure on the same train and test data sets, we reach the results presented in Table II. More specifically, while maintaining almost equal forecasting performance in terms of Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE), it is evident that the reduced model significantly outperforms the initial one in terms of speed, achieving 32% reduction (i.e., from 1.67 ms to 1.13 ms) in inference time.

B. Counterfactual explanations for dynamic resource allocation

For the use case of dynamic resource allocation, we consider a cloud-native scenario with a single service composed of three (3) inter-linked microservices. The current state of the system consists of the resource utilization of each microservice (i.e., CPU and memory), while an AI model is employed to predict whether this state leads to a QoS (i.e., end-to-end service latency) violation. The behavior of the microservices and the corresponding latency is based on real data from Online Boutique experiments of the BARO dataset [15], where various system metrics are recorded while artificial failures

TABLE II: Performance comparison between General and Reduced model

	Initial LSTM	Reduced LSTM
Features	4	2
Lookback Window	36	12
RMSE	0.037	0.035
MAE	0.017	0.015
Inference Time	1.67ms	1.13ms

are introduced on the microservices, causing high end-to-end latency.

In this experiment, we want to showcase how counterfactual explanations can provide an actionable solution to avoid QoS violations, by suggesting the optimal change in resource allocation that leads to an acceptable QoS. To that end, we have implemented a *genetic algorithm* that solves an optimization problem by searching for the minimum change in the current resource utilization state. This change in resource utilization in CPU, memory or both can then easily be translated into the number of millicores and MB to be allocated to the corresponding microservice(s). In addition, we have implemented two baseline horizontal auto-scaling approaches, commonly employed for orchestration in cloud-edge environments: *i) Service Horizontal Auto-scaling (SHA)*, which scales up the whole service by doubling its resources, and *ii) Microservice Horizontal Auto-scaling (MHA)*, which only scales up specific microservices that potentially cause the latency violation, again by doubling their allocated resources.

The results of our experiments for three different cases (C1-C3) are provided in Table III, considering initial allocations of 100 mcores (CPU) and 100 MB (memory) for each microservice. For each of the three cases, the counterfactual-based genetic algorithm identifies and allocates the minimum amount of additional resources precisely where they are needed. As we can see in the table, in cases where a specific microservice can face both CPU and memory issues (e.g., C1), counterfactual explanations provide approximately 81% (18.14 vs. 100 mcores) and 54% (46.23 vs. 100 MB) CPU and memory gains, respectively, compared to the MHA scheme, while the gains can reach up to 93% (CPU) and 81% (memory) compared to the SHA scheme. In addition, we can also see that, in cases where one microservice has only CPU (e.g., C2) or memory (e.g., C3) issues, the gains are even more significant, as the baseline schemes fail to identify the root of the problem, scaling either the microservice (MHA) or the whole service (SHA) by allocating both CPU and memory.

VI. CONCLUSION

The importance of XAI in providing transparent and interpretable AI decisions is growing rapidly as AI is increasingly adopted in cloud-native network and service orchestration. In such scenarios, the type of the data (typically tabular, time-series, or raw text) dictates the selection of AI methods and, consequently, the appropriate XAI techniques to apply. This article has presented an initial effort to establish a framework to connect data types and the corresponding XAI techniques. In addition, we have listed various use cases within cloud-native networks, illustrating how XAI can bring important

TABLE III: Gains of Counterfactual-based auto-scaling compared to baseline approaches

Cases	MS #1		MS #2		MS #3		Counterfactual		MHA		SHA	
	CPU (%)	Mem. (%)	CPU (%)	Mem. (%)	CPU (%)	Mem. (%)	CPU (mcores)	Mem. (MB)	CPU (mcores)	Mem. (MB)	CPU (mcores)	Mem. (MB)
C1	8.85	15.48	2.85	8.16	94.51	87.74	18.14	46.23	100	100	3x100	3x100
C2	99.76	15.10	3.23	8.45	35.96	11.29	24.70	0	100	100	3x100	3x100
C3	21.19	15.42	2.57	8.40	38.78	98.91	0	41.30	100	100	3x100	3x100

benefits. To demonstrate these gains, we have presented two proof-of-concept scenarios (i.e., AI model reduction for workload forecasting and dynamic resource allocation), highlighting that XAI can significantly improve model inference time and resource efficiency (CPU and memory) in cloud-native environments. Our work marks an important first step in bridging the gap between theoretical model interpretability and practical AI deployment, paving the way for more transparent and trustworthy AI applications in the evolving landscape of 6G technology and edge/cloud computing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the EC projects ELIXIRION (101120135), VERGE (SNS-JU-101096034), ETHER (SNS-JU-101096526), CloudSkin (101092646) and CLOUDSTARS (101086248) under the Horizon Europe programme. It has been also supported by the projects AEON-ZERO (TSI-063000-2021-52), FREE-6G (TSI-063000-2021-144), AROMA3D (TSI-063000-2021-70/71), 6G-OASIS (TSI-063000-2021-24), SUCCESS-6G (TSI-063000-2021-39/40/41) and AVANZANDO-5G-GEMELOS DIGITALES (TSI-063000-2021-112/113/114) under the UNICO5G-RPTR programme.

BIOGRAPHIES

Lazaros Liatsas is Research Engineer and MSCA doctoral candidate at Nearby Computing, currently pursuing a Ph.D. in Signal Theory and Communications at UPC. His Ph.D. research focuses on eXplainable AI and its applications in service orchestration for cloud/edge scenarios.

Dr. Godfrey M. Kibalya is Senior Researcher at Nearby Computing. He holds an M.Sc. in Telecommunications Engineering from the University of Trento and a Ph.D. degree from UPC. His research interests focuses on AI-driven network and service management.

Dr. Angelos Antonopoulos is the R&I Director at Nearby Computing. He received the Ph.D. from the Signal Theory and Communications department of UPC. He has authored over 130 papers on several topics, including network management, edge computing and 5G/6G networking. He has led several research projects and received awards for his work.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Wang, C.-L. I, J. Sun, X. Sun, and S. Chen, "End to End AI Architecture for Next Generation Network," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 86–92, Feb. 2024.
- [2] The Business Research Company, "AI in Telecommunication Global Market Report," Jan. 2024.
- [3] S. Wang, M. A. Qureshi, L. Miralles-Pechuán, T. Huynh-The, T. R. Gadekallu, and M. Liyanage, "Explainable AI for 6G Use Cases: Technical Aspects and Research Challenges," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 5, pp. 2490–2540, Apr. 2024.
- [4] S. K. Jagatheesaperumal, Q.-V. Pham, R. Ruby, Z. Yang, C. Xu, and Z. Zhang, "Explainable AI Over the Internet of Things (IoT): Overview, State-of-the-Art and Future Directions," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 3, pp. 2106–2136, Oct. 2022.
- [5] S. Garg, K. Kaur, G. S. Aujla, G. Kaddoum, P. Garigipati, and M. Guizani, "Trusted Explainable AI for 6G-enabled Edge Cloud Ecosystem," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 163–170, 2023.
- [6] M. Scott, L. Su-In *et al.*, "A Unified Approach to Interpreting Model Predictions," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 30, pp. 4765–4774, Dec. 2017.
- [7] M. T. Ribeiro, S. Singh, and C. Guestrin, "Why Should I Trust You?" Explaining the Predictions of Any Classifier," *22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, Aug. 2016.
- [8] I. Stepin, J. M. Alonso, A. Catala, and M. Pereira-Fariña, "A Survey of Contrastive and Counterfactual Explanation Generation Methods for Explainable Artificial Intelligence," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 11974–12001, Jan. 2021.
- [9] M. Sundararajan, A. Taly, and Q. Yan, "Axiomatic Attribution for Deep Networks," *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pp. 3319–3328, Aug. 2017.
- [10] R. R. Selvaraju, M. Cogswell, A. Das, R. Vedantam, D. Parikh, and D. Batra, "Grad-CAM: Visual Explanations From Deep Networks via Gradient-Based Localization," *IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, Oct. 2017.
- [11] A. Shrikumar, P. Greenside, and A. Kundaje, "Learning Important Features Through Propagating Activation Differences," *International conference on machine learning*, pp. 3145–3153, Aug. 2017.
- [12] M. Ameer, B. Brik, and A. Ksentini, "Leveraging LLMs to eXplain DRL Decisions for Transparent 6G Network Slicing," *IEEE 10th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, June 2024.
- [13] B. J. Gort, G. M. Kibalya, M. A. Serrano, and A. Antonopoulos, "Forecasting Trends in Cloud-Edge Computing: Unleashing the Power of Attention Mechanisms," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 2024.
- [14] S. Shen, V. Van Beek, and A. Iosup, "Statistical Characterization of Business-critical Workloads Hosted in Cloud Datacenters," *2015 15th IEEE/ACM international symposium on cluster, cloud and grid computing*, pp. 465–474, May. 2015.
- [15] L. Pham, H. Ha, and H. Zhang, "BARO: Robust Root Cause Analysis for Microservices via Multivariate Bayesian Online Change Point Detection," *Proc. ACM Softw. Eng.*, vol. 1, no. FSE, Jul. 2024.